

Effect of emulsifiable concentrate (EC) insecticides on tungro virus infection and *N. virescens* mortality,^a Cuttack, India.

Insecticide		Prevention of infection (%)		Insect mortality ^b (%)	
Common name	Trade name	1 DAT	5 DAT	1 DAT	5 DAT
Trial 1					
Cypermethrin	Ripcord 10 EC	100 a	100 a	100 a	100 a
DDT	Hildit 25 EC	64 b	32 c	100 a	64 b
Fenitrothion-1	Accothion 50 EC	61 bc	27 c	100 a	70 b
Vamidothion	Vamidothion 30 EC	60 bc	60 b	100 a	100 a
Malathion	Cythion 50 EC	50 c	6 de	100 a	58 b
Phosalone	Zolone 35 EC	37 d	0 e	100 a	100 a
Fenitrothion-2	Folithion 50 EC	19 e	15 cd	72 b	12 c
Methyl parathion	Metacid 50 EC	18 e	20 cd	39 c	7 c
Dichlorvos	Nuvan 100 EC	16 e	12 cd	100 a	100 a
Endosulfan	Hildan 35 EC	1 f	0 e	5 d	3 c
Trial 2					
FMC 35001	Marshall 25 EC	92 a	77 a	100 a	100 a
Ofunack	Ofunack 40 EC	85 a	46 b	100 a	100 a
Monocrotophos	Nuvacon 40 EC	15 b	11 c	97 a	26 b
Dimethoate	Rogor 35 EC	15 b	42 b	65 b	38 b
Formothion	Anthio 25 EC	10 b	6 cd	77 b	11 c
Diazinon	Bazanon 20 EC	9 b	10 cd	80 b	20 bc
Chlorpyrifos	Dursban 20 EC	0 c	0 d	6 c	0 d
Trial 3					
Phosphamidon	Dimecron 40 EC	88 a	61 a	100 a	100 a
Demeton-O-methyl	Metasystox 25 EC	82 a	58 a	100 a	100 a
BPMC	Sulphoxide BPMC 50 EC	62 b	48 ab	88 b	81 b
Quinalphos	Ekalux 25 EC	42 c	22 bc	100 a	53 c
Fenitrothion	Folithion 50 EC	25 d	15 cde	65 c	53 c
Thiometon	Ekatin 25 EC	24 d	7 de	90 a	53 c
Methyl parathion	Paratox 50 EC	17 de	20 bcd	28 d	5 f
Phenthoate-1	Elsan 50 EC	17 de	5 e	89 b	14 e
Carbaryl	Sevimol 40 EC	15 de	8 cde	94 ab	29 d
Phenthoate-2	Phendal50 EC	11 e	6 de	100 a	100 a

^a DAT = days after treatment. Values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at P = 0.05 by DMRT. ^b Adjusted values by Abbott's formula

Of 10 insecticides tested in trial 1, cypermethrin prevented virus infection at 1 and 5 DAT. Vamidothion provided 60% prevention at 1 and 5 DAT. DDT, fenitrothion-1, and malathion gave some protection at 1 DAT, but little at 5 DAT. Cypermethrin, vamidothion, phosalone, and dichlorvos caused 100% vector mortality at 1 and 5 DAT. DDT, fenitrothion-1, and malathion caused 100% mortality at 1 DAT.

In trial 2, FMC 35001 effectively prevented infection and caused vector mortality. Ofunack was next best. The remaining insecticides neither prevented virus infection nor controlled the vector.

In trial 3 phosphamidon and demeton-O-methyl prevented infection and caused 100% *N. virescens* mortality. Phenthoate-2 controlled the vector at 1 and 5 DAT, but did not prevent infection.

Results indicate that some insecticides that controlled the vector did not prevent virus infection. Phosalone, dichlorvos, and phenthoate-2 killed the vector, but did not prevent infection. This phenomenon needs to be investigated. Cypermethrin, vamidothion, FMC 35001, ofunack, phosphamidon, and demeton-O-methyl prevented virus infection and controlled the vector effectively. ✨

Antagonistic effects of soil microorganisms on rice sheath blight pathogen

A. M. Rosales, research aide, and T. W. Mew, plant pathologist, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

The effects of microorganisms associated with rice sheath blight pathogen on the latter's survival on dryland and wetland culture were investigated.

A *Trichoderma* sp. colonizing the sclerotial bodies of *Thanatephorus*

cucumeris in a dryland rice field was isolated and tested for antagonistic activity against the pathogen. On potato dextrose agar (PDA), an inhibition zone was formed between *Trichoderma* and *T. cucumeris*. Pathogen growth stopped after contact with *Trichoderma*. *Trichoderma* continued growing and eventually covered the whole plate.

Microscopic examination showed that *Trichoderma* frequently coiled around aerial hyphae of *T. cucumeris* on the agar surface. No coiling around subsur-

face hyphae was observed. Scientists observed that: 1) many short branches were produced by the main hyphae of *Trichoderma* and that each branch coiled tightly around the pathogen's hyphae, 2) the main hyphae coiled around the pathogen's hyphae, and the coils formed at a narrower angle with few coils per unit length of hypha, 3) the *Trichoderma* hyphae grew parallel to *T. cucumeris* hyphae and at intervals produced short branches that coiled around the pathogen's hypha. Further examina-

tion showed cytoplasm vacuolation, and coagulation followed by hyphae bursting.

Bacteria with different colony types were isolated from sheath blight sclerotia and tested in petri dishes to study their antagonistic activities against *T. cucumeris*. Many isolates were antagonistic. Some inhibited mycelial growth and caused browning of hyphal tips. Microscopic examination showed that necrosis of hyphae occurred. Hyphae remained intact but nonviable, and protoplasm was agglutinated and pigmented.

Isolate 17 prevented lesion develop

Effect of antagonistic bacteria on incidence and severity of sheath blight in the IRRI greenhouse.^a

Treatment	Incidence ^b (%)	Severity (lesion length, cm)
Isolate 17 + pathogen	30	0.61
Isolate 24 + pathogen	75	1.27
Pathogen alone	100	2.00

Bacterial suspension (1×10^6 cells/ml) was sprayed at the basal portion 1 day before inoculation. ^bIncidence based on number of tillers infected divided by total number of tillers: 3 hills/replication; 3 replications/treatment.

ment when sprayed on detached rice flag leaves before, after, and simultaneously

with inoculation of the pathogen. Sclerotial bodies soaked in a suspension of bacterial isolate 17 for 2 weeks were not viable. Bodies treated with isolate 24 showed an abrupt germination decline (63.3% to 26.7%) at 0 and 2-week sampling periods. Twenty percent of the sclerotia soaked in isolate 24 for 6 weeks were viable.

Preliminary greenhouse test results showed isolate 17 sprayed at the basal portion of the rice plants 1 day before inoculation was superior to isolate 24 for reducing sheath blight incidence and inhibiting lesion development (see table). ✎

Host range of rice gall dwarf virus

Methie Putta and Dara Chettanachit, Rice Pathology Branch, Division of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Department of Agriculture (RPB-DPPM-DA), Bangkok; Toshihiro Omura, Institute for Plant Virus Research (IPVR), Tsukuba Science City; Hitoshi Inoue, Kyushu National Agricultural Experiment Station, Chikugo, Fukuoka 833, Japan; Tadashi Morinaka, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Tsukuba Science City; Yohachiro Honda and Yasuo Saito, IPVR, Tsukuba Science City, Yatabe, Ibaraki 305, Japan; and Somkid Disthaporn, RPB-DPPM-DA, Bangkok, Thailand

A new rice virus disease that causes stunting, dark green leaf discoloration,

and presence of galls along the leaf blades and leaf sheaths was identified as rice gall dwarf virus (RGDV) in Thailand in 1979.

Second- and third-instar nymphs of rice green leafhopper *Nephotettix nigropictus* that had fed on infected rice plants for 2 to 3 days were reared on healthy TN1 seedlings for 10 to 14 days, then *N. nigropictus* was used to inoculate 11 plant species grown in pots: maize *Zea mays*, sorghum *Sorghum nervosum*, timothy grass *Phleum pratense*, orchard grass *Dactylis glomerata*, Italian rye-grass *Lolium multiflorum*, Japanese grass *Alopecurus aequalis* var. *amurensis*, wild rice *Oryza rufipogon*, barley *Hordeum distichum*, wheat *Triticum aestivum*, rye *Secale cereale*, and oat *Avena sativa*. At the second leaf

stage seedling were inoculated by placing 2 viruliferous insects on each plant for 2 to 3 days.

Virus symptoms developed 15 to 30 days after inoculation. Inoculated plants were examined by electron microscope using a negative stain preparation, then were back-inoculated to healthy rice seedlings. Barley, wheat, rye, oat, Italian ryegrass, Japanese grass, and wild rice showed typical symptoms. Polyhedral particles 65 nm in diameter were observed in the negatively stained preparation. Rice plants exhibited symptoms after back-inoculation.

Maize, sorghum, timothy grass, and orchard grass did not show symptoms. No particles were observed under the electron microscope, nor did symptoms appear after back-inoculation. ✎

Weed host of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, a rice sheath blight pathogen

D. C. Khatua, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Cooch Behar, West Bengal, India

During July 1982 *Echinochloa colona*, a common rice field weed, was severely

infected with *R. solani* in some fields in the Cooch Behar district of West Bengal and the Goalpara district of Assam.

Both areas are in high-rainfall zones (more than 300 cm/year). The infected weed was growing in rice fields with 20-25 cm standing water, and on the boun-

dary ridges of the fields. Soil pH was between 5.5 and 6.5. Rice plants were moderately affected by the disease.

R. solani isolates from this weed species have been found to infect artificially inoculated rice. ✎

Decline in number and viability of sclerotia of rice stem rot fungus in soil

J. P. Yadav and R. S. Mehrotra, Botany Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132119, India

Sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae* Catt., the causal pathogen of rice stem rot disease, were produced on a sterile rice-rice hull mixture and used to artificially infest soil from a wet fallow field.

Seventy-nine mg of sclerotia were weighed and mixed thoroughly into 3 kg

of sandy loam soil in pots by sprinkling the sclerotia on the soil surface and thoroughly mixing the soil using a hand-operated rototiller. Propagules (sclerotia) were introduced at the rate of about 5 sclerotia/g of soil, which corresponds to a moderate infestation level. There